

An iterative method for quaternionic linear equations

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Abstract : By real representation of the quaternionic matrix, an iterative method for quaternionic linear equations $Ax = b$ is proposed. Then the convergence conditions are obtained. At last, a numerical example is given to illustrate the efficiency of this method.

Keywords : quaternionic linear equations, Real representation, iterative algorithm.

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